

NOTES

Investigations on Cyanogen Derivatives of Molybdenum

H. K. SAHA*, B. C. SAHA and T. K. RAYCHAUDHURI

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory, Pure Chemistry Department, University College of Science, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 31 August 1988, revised 8 March 1989, accepted 25 April 1989

It is known that molybdenum forms quite a number of hydroxocyanides¹⁻³ specially in higher oxidation states. The so-called 'red and blue' cyanides have been the subject of great confusion to a number of investigators. Wardlaw and his coworkers described the composition of red cyanide as $K_4[Mo(OH)_4(CN)_4] \cdot 4H_2O$ and blue cyanide as $K_3[Mo(OH)_3(CN)_4 \cdot H_2O] \cdot 2H_2O$, which have been repudiated by other workers². Some workers⁴ also claimed that Wardlaw's blue cyanide is a paramagnetic compound and formulated as $K_3[Mo(OH)_4(CN)_4] \cdot 2H_2O$ accordingly containing pentavalent molybdenum. An alternate formulation suggested by the same workers appeared in the literature as $K_3[MoO_2(CN)_4 \cdot (H_2O)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$.

It appears to the present authors that the formulations $K_3[Mo(OH)_3(CN)_4 \cdot H_2O] \cdot 2H_2O$ and $K_3[Mo(OH)_4(CN)_4] \cdot 2H_2O$ are the same. It is also clear from the literature that molybdenum assumes octacoordination with dodecahedral configuration in its cyanogen compounds, where a d^4sp^3 hybridisation would evidently render the quadrivalent state as a diamagnetic one. Therefore, in order to avoid this confusion the present authors have conclusively established the existence of the anion $[Mo(OH)_4(CN)_4]^{4-}$ by the isolation of salts and study of the salts of different metals.

In our recent investigations of the chemistry of molybdenum in higher oxidation states hydroxocyanides have been studied by us. The so-called 'blue cyanide' was prepared by us following Wardlaw's method and it has been found to be diamagnetic. It has not been possible so far to prepare any paramagnetic hydroxocyanide. The composition of the 'blue cyanide' has been established by us by the isolation and characterisation of the salts of silver, copper, cobalt, nickel and uranium.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade. Copper, silver, nickel, cobalt and uranium were estimated⁵ gravimetrically as copper oxide, silver chloride, nickel dimethylglyoxime, cobalt sulphate and uranium oxide respectively after digesting the

individual salt with proper reagents. In each case the filtrate and washings were used for the estimation of molybdenum. Molybdenum in the filtrate and washings was first precipitated as molybdenum sulphide and then ignited and weighed as MoO_3 . Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method.

Preparation of complexes :

$Cu_2[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$: An aqueous solution of copper sulphate (1.5 g) was added to an ice-cold aqueous solution of $K_4[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$ (1 g) in molar ratio 2 : 1. The resulting violet crystalline solid was washed and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, (1.8 g).

$Ag_4[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$: $K_4[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$ (2 g) was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and cooled in ice. It was added to an aqueous solution containing silver nitrate (3 g) in molar ratio 1 : 4. The resulting brown crystalline solid was washed and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, (2.2 g).

$Ni_2[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$: An aqueous solution of nickel nitrate (1.6 g) was added to an ice-cold aqueous solution of $K_4[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$ (2 g) in molar ratio 2 : 1 with stirring. The resulting pale green crystalline solid was washed repeatedly with cold water and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, (1.7 g).

$Co_2[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$: An aqueous solution of cobalt chloride (1.2 g) was added dropwise to an ice-cold aqueous solution of $K_4[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$ (2 g) in molar ratio 2 : 1. The resulting chocolate brown crystalline solid was washed and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, (1.3 g).

$(UO_2)_2[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$: Uranyl nitrate (~0.5 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of dilute nitric acid was added dropwise to an ice-cold aqueous solution of $K_4[Mo(CN)_4(OH)_4]$ (0.5 g) in molar ratio 2 : 1. The resulting brown crystalline solid was washed repeatedly with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, (0.5 g).

The complexes were characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis, magnetic moment at 27° (Table 1) and ir and electronic spectral data.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra of all these complexes exhibit strong ν_{C-N} bands⁶ in the range 2 020–2 140 cm^{-1} . The diffuse reflectance spectra of all of the complexes show maxima around 19 200–22 700, 16 000–17 200 [$A_1(d_{x^2-y^2}) \rightarrow E(d_{x^2-y^2}) (d_{z^2, yz})$] and 13 200–13 900 cm^{-1} [$A_1(d_{x^2-y^2}) \rightarrow B_1(d_{x^2-y^2}) (d_{z^2})$]. The results could be interpreted on the basis of dodecahedral arrangement of the ligand around the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
		Mo	Metal	N	
$\text{Cu}_2[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Violet	24.02	31.95	14.01	2.0
		(24.30)	(32.15)	(14.17)	
$\text{Ag}_4[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Brown	13.64	62.20	7.40	Dia.
		(13.71)	(61.71)	(8.00)	
$\text{Ni}_2[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Pale green	24.60	29.84	7.00	3.3
		(24.91)	(30.46)	(7.26)	
$\text{Co}_2[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Chocolate brown	24.56	29.99	7.02	4.8
		(24.89)	(30.53)	(7.26)	
$(\text{UO}_2)_2[\text{Mo}(\text{ON})_4(\text{OH})_4]$	Brown	11.36	58.20	6.40	Dia.
		(11.88)	(58.90)	(6.90)	

central metal ion of these octacoordinated complexes, where d -orbital splits into four levels⁶, $B_1(d_{x^2-y^2}) < A_1(d_{z^2}) < E(d_{xz}, d_{yz}) < B_2(d_{xy})$. The spectra closely resembled those obtained for similar systems⁷.

References

1. W. B. BUCKNALL and W. WARDLAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2981.
2. M. C. STEELE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1957, 10, 406.
3. H. K. SAHA, B. C. SAHA and S. S. MONDAL, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1975, 412, 179.
4. W. P. GRIFFITH, J. LEWIS and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 872.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis Including Instrumental Analysis", 1961, pp. 486, 479, 530, 540.
6. J. D. SWALEN and J. A. IBERS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, 37, 17.
7. M. BASU and S. BASU, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 2461.

Coordination Template Reactions. Part-V.
Complexes of Macrocyclic Ligand Dibenzo-
[c, j]-1,6,9,14-tetraazacyclohexadeca-
1,6,8,13-tetraene with Copper(II) and
Nickel(II) Ions

(Mrs.) P. R. SHUKLA*, (Miss) SADHNA SRIVASTAVA
and

NIHAL AHMAD

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University,
Lucknow-226 007

and

GOPAL NARAIN

Chemistry Department, Dr. Hari Singh Gaur University,
Sagar-470 003

*Manuscript received 1 August 1988, revised 30 January 1989,
accepted 18 April 1989*

A large number of transition metal complexes derived from macrocycles obtained by the self-condensation of three or four molecules of *o*-aminobenzaldehyde have been reported¹⁻⁴. In the

present communication, an attempt has been made to use *m*-aminobenzaldehyde, for which self-condensation is expected to be less favourable and hence, the aldehyde has been initially condensed with ethylenediamine and finally with glyoxal to result in a closed ring tetradentate N_4 donor (L) which forms planar complexes with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} .

Experimental

The complexes were prepared in three steps.

N,N'-Bis(3-nitrophenyl)ethylenediamine (1): To a solution of ethylenediamine (0.01 mol, 0.60 ml) in methanol was added *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.02 mol, 3.0 ml) slowly with constant stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting yellow crystals were filtered, washed with methanol, dried and analysed (Table 1).

N,N'-Bis(3-aminophenyl)ethylenediamine (2): 1 was reduced with Sn/HCl solution and the resulting product (2) precipitated out as amine hydrochloride, was washed with water, methanol and used as such.

Preparation of complexes: Compound 2 (0.01 mol, 0.27 g) in methanol was mixed with appropriate metal(II) salt (0.01 mol). pH of the solution was adjusted to 6-7 and refluxed for 8 h. A solution of glyoxal (0.01 mol, 0.58 ml) in methanol was then added to it and the solution was further refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was purified by running over tlc plates and the complexes were crystallised out using petroleum ether-acetone mixture and analysed (Table 1).

Preparation of free macrocycle (L): The free macrocycle was obtained by extricating out nickel from the nickel(II) chloride complex by the following method. Nickel(II) chloride complex (0.01 mol) in methanol was refluxed for 2 h with potassium cyanide (0.04 mol) in water. The resulting precipitate of $[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ was filtered over a silica column; the resulting solution was run over tlc plates and the free macrocycle crystallised out by using petroleum ether and characterised (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis and molar conductance data reveal the molecular formulae of the complexes as $[\text{M}(\text{L})\text{X}_2]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} ; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, SCN^- , ClO_4^- , BF_4^- ; $\text{L} = \text{dibenzo}[c, j]-1,6,9,14\text{-tetraazacyclohexadeca-1,6,8,13-tetraene}$ ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4$). The complexes dissolve in methanol to give conducting solutions thus suggesting that the anions are not coordinated.

The molecular formulae of the three products 1, 2 and L has been assigned on the basis of their elemental analysis data (Table 1). In their ir spectra, strong absorptions are observed in the range 2900-2700 and 1600-1450 cm^{-1} which correspond to CH and aromatic ring vibrations. In the spectra of